

TO STUDY THE COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF ULTRASOUND VIS A VIS MRI IN SHOULDER PATHOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: *The shoulder joint, characterized by its wide range of motion, is prone to a variety of pathologies due to its inherent compromise between stability and mobility. While MRI is considered the gold standard for evaluating shoulder pathologies, its limitations, including cost and accessibility, underscore the need for alternative diagnostic modalities like ultrasound (USG). This study aims to compare the diagnostic efficacy of USG and MRI in evaluating shoulder pathologies, with a focus on rotator cuff abnormalities.*

Methods: *This single-center, prospective study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis at Chhatrapati Shivaji Subharti Hospital, Meerut, over 1 year and 9 months. After obtaining ethical approval, 120 patients with clinical suspicion of shoulder pathologies were recruited. Patients underwent USG using a Samsung HS70A machine and MRI using a uMR 780 3.0T scanner with standardized imaging protocols. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy were calculated for both modalities. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Version 25.*

Results: *USG demonstrated high sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy in detecting full-thickness and partial-thickness rotator cuff tears, with comparable performance to MRI in diagnosing calcific tendinosis and subacromial impingement. However, MRI outperformed USG in characterizing tear extent, evaluating labral pathologies, and detecting minimal joint effusions. Non-rotator cuff pathologies, including ACJ arthropathy, bursitis, and biceps tendon disorders, were reliably identified by USG with high specificity, consistent with previous literature.*

Conclusion: *Ultrasound is a reliable, cost-effective diagnostic tool for shoulder pathologies, particularly for rotator cuff tears and dynamic evaluations, making it an excellent preliminary modality. MRI remains indispensable for detailed anatomical characterization and subtle pathologies, complementing USG for comprehensive shoulder assessments.*

Keywords: Shoulder Pathologies, Rotator Cuff Tears, Ultrasound, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Diagnostic Efficacy

Subject: Radiology

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INTRODUCTION

The shoulder joint, a marvel of biomechanics, is a ball-and-socket joint that offers unparalleled mobility, enabling movement in multiple planes. [1] This exceptional range of motion, however, comes at the cost of stability, making the shoulder prone to injuries and pathologies. To counterbalance its inherently unstable structure, the shoulder relies on the coordinated function of the rotator cuff, glenoid labrum, and the surrounding capsule. [2,3] Despite these safeguards, shoulder pain remains a pervasive musculoskeletal complaint, affecting 10–67% of the general population during their lifetime and ranking as the third most common cause of orthopedic consultations.[4,5]

The causes of shoulder pain are diverse, varying by age group. While younger individuals often experience biomechanical or inflammatory issues, older adults frequently suffer from rotator cuff-related disorders, with subacromial impingement syndrome as the leading culprit. [6,7] Understanding and diagnosing these conditions is complex, given the intricate interplay of bones, muscles, tendons, and nerves within the shoulder joint. [4] Traditionally, diagnosis relied on clinical evaluation, but the limitations of physical examination, particularly for peri-articular conditions, have prompted the adoption of imaging modalities such as X-rays, ultrasonography (USG), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). [8]

Plain radiographs provide foundational insights into bony structures but fall short in assessing soft tissues. MRI, widely regarded as the gold standard, offers unparalleled detail of the shoulder's anatomy, enabling accurate diagnosis of rotator cuff tears, labral injuries, and other soft tissue abnormalities. However, its high cost, limited availability, and logistical challenges in certain populations (e.g., claustrophobic or obese patients) underscore the need for alternative imaging techniques. [8,9]

Ultrasonography, a non-invasive, cost-effective, and radiation-free modality, has emerged as a valuable tool in evaluating shoulder pathologies. With advancements in technology, high-resolution ultrasound achieves sensitivity and specificity rates exceeding 90% in detecting rotator cuff tears, rivaling MRI in many scenarios. Moreover, its ability to provide dynamic imaging and immediate results makes it particularly advantageous in clinical settings. [10,11]

This study aims to compare the diagnostic efficacy of ultrasonography against MRI in shoulder pathologies, focusing on rotator cuff abnormalities. By correlating the findings of both modalities, this research seeks to validate ultrasound as a reliable and accessible preliminary diagnostic tool in shoulder imaging.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Place of Study:

This study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Imaging & Interventional Radiology at Chhatrapati Shivaji Subharti Hospital, affiliated with Swami Vivekanand Subharti University, Meerut, after obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee.

Duration of Study:

The study spanned 1 year and 9 months, from August 2022 to May 2024.

Study Design:

This was a single-center, prospective, qualitative study aimed at evaluating the diagnostic efficacy of ultrasonography (USG) compared to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for shoulder pathologies.

Study Population:

Patients referred to the Department of Radiodiagnosis from OPD, IPD, or the Emergency Department with clinical suspicion of shoulder pathologies were included.

Sample Size:

A purposive non-probability sampling method was used to select 120 adult patients, ensuring unbiased representation within the defined study criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients referred for MRI and USG evaluation with clinical suspicion of shoulder pathology.
- Incidentally diagnosed cases.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients refusing participation.
- Contraindications for MRI (e.g., pacemakers, metallic implants, claustrophobia).
- Known cases of shoulder pathology.

Procedure:

After clinical history and relevant examinations, patients underwent USG using the Samsung HS70A machine with a linear probe (7–12 MHz frequency). This was followed by MRI on a uMR 780 3.0T scanner using a dedicated shoulder coil. Standardized imaging protocols were followed for both modalities to evaluate the biceps tendon, rotator cuff, labrum, and other associated structures.

USG Criteria:

- **Tears:** Full-thickness and partial-thickness tears were identified based on echogenicity, tendon continuity, and bursal involvement.
- **Non-tear pathologies:** Tendinosis, bursitis, impingement, and calcifications were evaluated using established sonographic markers.

MRI Criteria:

- **Tears:** High signal intensity on T2-weighted images indicating fluid-filled defects.
- **Non-tear pathologies:** Capsular thickening, tendon degeneration, and subacromial space narrowing were assessed using multi-sequence imaging.

Statistical Analysis:

Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 25. Descriptive statistics, including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy, were calculated.

A 55-year-old male patient presented with a limited range of motion and painful arm abduction. Longitudinal sonography view (Fig 1A) of the right shoulder with subacromial impingement, during the active elevation of the arm halfway between flexion and abduction with hand in pronation, shows pooling of fluid in the lateral aspect of subacromial- subdeltoid bursa (*arrow*).

Coronal PD FS (Fig 1 B) image shows Partial thickness bursal aspect (block arrow) supraspinatus insertional tear. Large inferiorly projecting osteophyte (curved arrow) from a degenerate AC joint indenting the supraspinatus musculotendinous junction.

A 40-year-old female patient presented with sudden onset pain in the anterior shoulder with intense pain in shoulder movements.

A longitudinal sonographic view (Fig 2A) of the supraspinatus tendon shows calcific deposits (block arrow) with a hypoechoic area (curved arrow) representing tendinosis.

Corresponding MR – T2 coronal image (Fig 2B) shows thickened supraspinatus footprint (line arrow) with T2-hyperintense intrasubstance degeneration (pentagon arrow), compatible with tendinopathy, calcific deposit is not identified.

A 30-year-old female presented with painful overhead abduction.

Longitudinal Ultrasound (Fig 3A) shows fluid in the subcoracoid bursa (block arrow) and Corresponding Axial T2 MR image (Fig 3B) show distended subcoracoid bursa with fluid signal intensity.

A 30 years old male patient with history of road traffic accident followed by severe pain in the anterior shoulder.

Longitudinal USG (Fig 4A) show full thickness tear of supraspinatus tendon with retraction of the tendon (arrow)

Corresponding MRI coronal PD-FS image (Fig 4B) show full thickness tear (block arrow) of supraspinatus tendon which is retracted and seen at the level of medial end of clavicle (curved arrow).

A 30-year-old presented with a history of trauma.

Short-axis ultrasound shows (Fig 5A) medial subluxation of the long head of the biceps tendon from the intertubercular groove (arrowhead), resting of the top of the lesser tuberosity. Block arrows show lesser tuberosity.

The corresponding Saggital T2 MR image (Fig 5B) shows medial subluxation of the long head of the biceps tendon (line arrow).

An eight years old male patient presented with pain in the anterior part of the shoulder with intermittent snapping sensation.

Short axis ultrasound (Fig 6A) (block arrow) show peribicipital fluid. Corresponding axial T2 MR image (Fig 6B) show peribicipital fluid consistent with biceps tenosynovitis.

A 45 year old female patient presented with restricted shoulder movements. Sonographic images (Fig 7A) show increased vascularity in the rotator interval (curved arrow) and axillary pouch thickening (Fig 7B) (double arrow) in the symptomatic shoulder as compared to the asymptomatic one.

Corresponding axial PD-FS image (Fig 7C) show replacement of normal rotator interval fat by soft-tissue signal (block arrow) secondary to granulation or fibrous tissue.

A 35-year-old male patient presented with a history of trauma.

Long axis USG (Fig 8A) shows exposure of the lesser tuberosity (black arrow) consistent with a complete full-thickness tear of the subscapularis tendon and corresponding MR axial T2 FS image (Fig 8B) shows full thickness tear of subscapularis tendon with proximal retraction of the torn tendon (black arrow).

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the majority of study participants were in the 21–30 years age group (35.7%), followed by 31–40 years (24.1%). The mean age of participants was 38.27 ± 13.33 years. Regarding gender, the study had a male predominance, with 66.1% male and 33.9% female participants.

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Age Group (in years)	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
<20	3	2.7
21-30	40	35.7
31-40	27	24.1
41-50	22	19.6
51-60	10	8.9
>60	10	8.9
Total	112	100
Mean±SD	38.27±13.33	
Gender		
Female	38	33.9
Male	74	66.1
Total	112	100.0

Correlation of USG & MRI findings for supraspinatus tendonpathologies.

Table 2 represents the diagnostic metrics for ultrasound (USG) in identifying shoulder pathologies. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy are compared across full-thickness tear (FTT), partial-thickness tear (PTT), and tendinosis (TS). The findings highlight USG's high accuracy and specificity, especially for full-thickness tears.

Pathology	TRUE +ve	FALSE +ve	TRUE -ve	FALSE -ve	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
FTT	7	0	104	1	87.5	100.0	100.00	99.05	99.11
PTT	8	2	100	2	88.89	97.09	72.73	99.01	91.11
TS	18	3	80	11	62.07	96.39	85.71	75.86	87.91

Correlation of USG & MRI findings for subscapularis tendonpathologies.

Table 3 illustrates the diagnostic metrics for ultrasound (USG) in evaluating subscapularis pathologies. Metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy are presented for full-thickness tear (FTT), partial-thickness tear (PTT), and tendinosis (TS). USG demonstrates exceptional performance with 100% accuracy for full-thickness tears, while specificity remains consistently high across all pathologies.

Pathology	TRUE +ve	FALSE +ve	TRUE -ve	FALSE -ve	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
FTT	2	0	110	0	100	100	100	100	100
PTT	4	0	106	1	80	100	100	99.07	99.1
TS	5	5	97	5	50	95.10	50	95.10	91.7

Correlation of USG & MRI findings for infraspinatus tendon pathologies.

Table 4 highlights the diagnostic performance of ultrasound (USG) for infraspinatus pathologies. Specificity is consistently 100% across all categories, but the sensitivity, positive predictive value (PPV), and accuracy for full-thickness tear (FTT) and partial-thickness tear (PTT) are non-applicable due to the absence of true-positive cases. Tendinosis (TS) shows a specificity of 100% and an accuracy of 98.21%.

Pathology	TRUE +ve	FALSE +ve	TRUE -ve	FALSE -ve	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
FTT	0	0	112	0	--	100.00	--	100.00	--
PTT	0	0	112	0	--	100.00	--	100	--
TS	0	0	110	2	0	100.00	--	98.21	98.21

Correlation of USG & MRI findings for Calcific tendinosis & subacromial impingement.

Table 5 compares the detection capabilities of ultrasound (USG) and MRI for calcific tendinosis and subacromial impingement. USG identified 5 cases of calcific tendinosis and 6 cases of subacromial impingement, whereas MRI did not detect any cases.

MODALITY	CALCIFIC TENDINOSIS(N)	SUBACROMIALIMPINGEMENT (N)
USG	5	6
MRI	0	0

Detailed correlation of pathological findings on USG and MRI for non-rotator rotator cuff pathologies.

Table 6 presents the diagnostic metrics for ultrasound (USG) in evaluating various non-rotator cuff pathologies. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy are compared across pathologies like ACJ arthropathy, bursitis, adhesive capsulitis, joint effusion, labral pathologies, and biceps tendon issues. USG exhibits high specificity and accuracy across most conditions, demonstrating its reliability in non-rotator cuff pathology detection.

Non rotator cuff pathology	MRI	USG	SENSITIVITY (%)	SPECIFICITY (%)	PPV(%)	NPV (%)	ACCURACY (%)
ACJ ARTHROPATHY	40	36	90	100	100	94.74	96.43
SUBACROMIAL SUBDELTOID BURSITIS	14	13	92.86	100	100	98.99	99.11
SUBCORACOID BURSITIS	28	18	64.29	100	100	90.38	91.80
ADHESIVE CAPSULITIS	5	3	60.00	100	100	98.17	98.21
JOINT EFFUSION	27	23	85.19	100	100	95.51	96.43
LABRAL PATHOLOGIES (INCLUDING BANKART’S& SLAP TEAR)	6	2	75	94.87	33.33	99.11	94.21
BICEPS TENDON PATHOLOGIES (INCLUDING TENOSYNOVITIS AND DISLOCATION/SUBLUXATION)	15	14	93.33	100	100	98.98	99.11

DISCUSSION

In our study, we evaluated that the majority of subjects were adults aged between 21 and 30 years, with traumatic events being the primary contributors to shoulder pathologies in this age group. These findings align with studies by *Onyambu C.K. et al.*[12] and *Chudasama S. et al.* [13], which also reported a predominance of shoulder pathologies in young adults. Gender analysis revealed a male predominance (66.1%), consistent with findings from studies by *Pankaj Chaudhari et al.* [3] and *Onyambu C.K. et al.*[12]

Regarding Subscapularis Tendon Pathologies, Full-Thickness Tears, USG demonstrated 100% sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy in detecting full-thickness tears of the subscapularis tendon. This contradicts *Selvaraj SS et al.*[10], who reported 85.71% sensitivity and 100% specificity, and *Fischer et al.* [14], who reported lower accuracy (77.8%). The difference in findings is likely due to the small sample size (only 2 cases) in the present study. In terms of Partial-Thickness Tears, USG achieved 80% sensitivity, 100% specificity, 100% PPV, 99.07% NPV, and 99.1% accuracy for partial-thickness tears. One case was misdiagnosed as tendinosis by USG. These findings are similar to *Selvaraj SS et al.*[10], who reported comparable diagnostic accuracy for partial-thickness tears. Regarding Tendinosis, USG showed lower diagnostic performance for tendinosis, with 50% sensitivity, 95.10% specificity, and 91.7% accuracy. These results align with studies by *Beggs I* [15] and *Saraya S et al.* [16], who also reported the limited ability of USG to detect rotator cuff tendinosis accurately.

In terms of Infraspinatus Tendon Pathologies, Only two cases of infraspinatus tendinosis were identified by MRI, both of which were missed by USG. The low sensitivity of USG in this study is attributable to the small sample size. This limitation is consistent with prior findings indicating the challenges of detecting subtle infraspinatus pathologies with USG.

Other Rotator Cuff Pathologies, Calcific Tendinosis, USG detected calcific deposits in 5 cases (27.7%) of supraspinatus tendinosis, which were missed by MRI. Studies by *Zubler et al.* [17], *Hartig and Huth et al.*[18], and *Chiou et al.*[19] also demonstrated USG's superior sensitivity for detecting calcific tendinosis compared to MRI. The inability of MRI to reliably differentiate calcifications from artifacts explains its lower sensitivity in such cases.

Regarding Subacromial Impingement, USG diagnosed 6 cases of subacromial impingement through dynamic evaluation, which were not identified by MRI. However, MRI identified the underlying bony causes, such as ACJ arthropathy and subacromial spurs. This finding aligns with *El-Shewi IE et al. [20]*, who reported USG's superiority in dynamic assessments, while MRI excelled in evaluating bony pathologies.

Regarding Non-Rotator Cuff Pathologies, ACJ arthropathy was the most common non-rotator cuff pathology observed. USG demonstrated 90% sensitivity and 100% specificity, consistent with the findings of *El-Shewi IE et al.[20] and Iagnocco et al. [21]*, who highlighted the accuracy of USG for ACJ evaluation. In terms of Adhesive Capsulitis, USG showed 60% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and 98.21% accuracy for adhesive capsulitis. Diagnosis was based on thickened axillary pouch and reduced sliding of the infraspinatus tendon during dynamic assessment. These results are comparable to studies by *Tandon A et al.[22] and Lee JC et al.[23]*, which reported the high reliability of USG for diagnosing adhesive capsulitis.

Regarding Biceps Tendon Pathologies, USG achieved 93.33% sensitivity and 100% specificity for detecting biceps tendon pathologies, including tenosynovitis and subluxation/dislocation. These findings align with studies by *Nathalie et al. [24] and Abdelzaher MG et al.[25]*, who reported USG's excellent diagnostic value in biceps tendon evaluations.

In terms of Bursitis and Joint Effusion, USG showed variable performance for bursitis and joint effusion. Sensitivity and specificity were 92.86% and 100% for subacromial-subdeltoid bursitis, 64.29% and 100% for subcoracoid bursitis, and 85.19% and 100% for joint effusion. Studies by *El-Shewi IE et al. [20], Singh P et al.[26], and McNally et al.[27]* corroborate these findings, highlighting USG's limitations in detecting minimal fluid but emphasizing its advantages in differentiating synovial thickening from fluid. USG detected 2 out of 6 cases of labral pathologies, achieving 75% sensitivity and 94.87% specificity. These findings contrast with studies by *Alali A et al. [28] and Martinoli C et al.[29]*, who reported better agreement between MRI and USG for detecting labral tears. The limited number of cases in this study likely contributed to the lower sensitivity of USG.

LIMITATIONS

This study, conducted on a small sample size from a single center, cannot be generalized to the entire Indian population, necessitating larger, multicenter studies. While USG demonstrated good sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy in detecting rotator cuff tears, MRI was superior in characterizing tear location and extent, as well as in diagnosing non-rotator cuff pathologies like labral tears, joint effusions, and ACJ arthropathy. However, MRI's limitations as a reference standard and lack of patient follow-up were noted.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that ultrasound (USG) is a reliable, cost-effective modality for diagnosing shoulder pathologies, particularly full-thickness and partial-thickness tears, with high sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy. USG proved superior to MRI in detecting calcific tendinosis and subacromial impingement through dynamic evaluation, while MRI excelled in characterizing tear extent, bony abnormalities, and labral pathologies. Despite its limitations in detecting subtle pathologies like tendinosis, USG serves as an efficient preliminary tool, complementing MRI's detailed structural assessment for comprehensive shoulder evaluations.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Consent: Written consent from participants has been obtained and preserved.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained and documented as per institutional guidelines.

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